

DIGITAL MARKETING AND BUYING BEHAVIOUR OF CONSUMERS OF ONLINE PRODUCTS IN ABIA STATE NIGERIA

¹Halim, Valentine Uche, ²Benson-Eluwa, Virginia Ph.D and ³Dr. Jude E. Madu

^{1,2}Department of Marketing Abia State University Uturu, Nigeria.

³Department of Business Management and Marketing Baze University Abuja, Nigeria.

***Email:** Valentyne-halim@yahoo.com/ Benson.eluwa@abiastateuniversity.edu.ng/*

Jude.madu@bazeuniversity.edu.ng

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Keywords: <i>Email, Mobile, Social Media, Digital, Consumer, Product.</i>	Abstract: <i>This study examined how digital marketing affects online product buyers in Umuahia and Aba in Abia State of Nigeria. Both primary and secondary data sources were employed in this study. The revised dataset underwent coding and subsequent analysis utilizing the statistical techniques of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) within the software platform SPSS 23.0. The empirical investigation unveiled a statistically significant association with digital marketing platforms namely: Email marketing, Online advertising, Social media marketing, and Mobile marketing, and the purchasing conduct of online product consumers situated in Abia state, Nigeria. The study proposes that diligent endeavors should be undertaken to augment and sustain the generation of conscious drive towards the effectiveness of email marketing in correlation with the purchasing patterns of online product consumers in Abia state, Nigeria. The implementation of this strategy will support a substantial enhancement of the financial viability of enterprises operating within the realm of digital trade, among other pertinent domains.</i>
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Background of the Study

Recent advancements and scholarly investigations have brought to light the fact that organizations, and indeed even entire nations, are progressively adopting digital platforms and technologies as a means to augment their management processes, thereby fostering innovation and yielding favorable financial outcomes (Castagna et al., 2020). In consideration of the aforementioned, it can be posited that digital marketing encompasses the

utilization of technological advancements in the realm of marketing endeavors and commercial undertakings, whereby the promotion of commodities and services, dissemination of information, endorsement of personalities, propagation of ideas, and exposure of locales are conducted via the internet, mobile devices, and various other electronic mediums (Pradhan et al., 2018). In light of this, Castagna et al. (2020) elucidated that digital marketing possesses the inherent capability to facilitate the process of

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locating and acquiring product ideas and information for both prospective and current consumers through the act of perusing the virtual realm or websites.

Moreover, it facilitates an environment conducive to the proficient and efficacious exchange of marketing communication with expansive cohorts of prospective and current clientele (Udih & Odibo, 2018). Furthermore, it is contended by scholars that digital marketing effectively facilitates the dissemination of valuable information and provision of services, thereby constituting an integral component of endeavors aimed at promoting the sale of goods and services. Schiffman and Kanuk (2007) posit that this phenomenon provides potential and current consumers with the chance to engage in interactive exchanges with diverse sources of customer information, enabling them to inquire, leave messages, and even directly initiate product orders with the pertinent stakeholders. In pursuit of this objective, Ugbuoshi (2013) unveiled that advanced nations across the globe are diligently leveraging their online platforms to promote their merchandise and services to clientele, facilitate customer order placement, and manage the process of order acquisition. In a similar vein, Udih and Odibo (2018) posited that the utilization of technology engenders temporal efficiencies, enhances the probability of securing optimal pricing, and affords enhanced security measures and superior payment alternatives. The internet serves as a universally accessible and interconnected digital realm that transcends geographical, physical, and spatial limitations, thereby eliminating barriers to

networking (Udih & Odibo, 2018). Henceforth, the global interconnectivity of computer systems affords individuals who are tethered to it the opportunity to avail themselves of an inexhaustible reservoir of data and engage in nearly instantaneous correspondence with any other individual similarly connected (Foskell & Ceserani, 2007 as cited in Udih & Odibo, 2018). Once more, the realm of digital marketing encompasses a diverse array of strategies and techniques, including but not limited to the utilization of social media platforms, websites, electronic marketing initiatives, as well as the employment of various forms of communicative marketing, such as opinion polls and game augmentation, all with the overarching objective of effectively engaging and capturing the attention of the desired target market (Garg et al., 2021). In the present investigation, the scholar embarked upon an exploration of the intricate dynamics underlying the impact of digital marketing channels, namely E-mail marketing, online advertising, and mobile marketing, on the intricate phenomenon of consumer purchasing behavior in the context of online products within the geographical confines of Abia state, Nigeria.

Accordingly, consumer purchasing behavior can be delineated as the cognitive, affective, and behavioral processes that individuals undertake when engaging in the process of product and service selection, acquisition, utilization, and disposal, with the ultimate aim of fulfilling their needs and desires (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2009). In a similar vein, it encompasses the procurement and various consumption-oriented endeavors

undertaken by individuals partaking in the process of economic exchange. The culmination of consumer buying behavior encompasses the intricate interplay of consumer preferences, perspectives, objectives, and determinations with regard to their market response when engaging in the purchase of a product or service (Roy & Datta, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

Digital marketing which includes email marketing and mobile marketing, have proven to be valuable tools for promoting products, facilitating effective and efficient interaction and communication between buyers and sellers, and gaining market share in a highly competitive market. These platforms operate continuously, providing services around the clock, seven days a week. According to Udih and Odibo (2018), the internet serves as a channel for directing digital marketing messages to the intended audience. This medium offers a convenient and cost-effective means for introducing and selling products, thereby enhancing a producer's competitive advantage and establishing a distinct market segment for the firm's products. In consideration of the aforementioned, the emergence of the internet, smart phones, and other electronic devices has undeniably facilitated individuals in accessing online platforms while on the move, thereby equipping them with immediate access to comprehensive information pertaining to the products and services being advertised. Henceforth, it is a matter of concern that the consumers, who are subjected to the utilization of these electronic devices within the confines of Abia state, exhibit

a deficiency in their understanding or possess a limited comprehension pertaining to the appropriate utilization of said devices for the purpose of engaging in online transactions for the procurement of goods and services. Individuals often opt for the conventional method of physically procuring goods in the open market, despite the availability of digital marketing platforms that enable them to conveniently place orders for products online from the comfort of their residences, with the added benefit of doorstep delivery. Once more, it is worth noting that remuneration for this particular transaction can be effectuated through the utilization of online payment methods, or alternatively, upon the physical receipt of the products, contingent upon the terms and conditions established in concordance with the service provider. In pursuit of this objective, the researcher was motivated to undertake this investigation, with the aim of elucidating the impact exerted by these digital marketing platforms (namely, Email marketing, social media marketing and Mobile Marketing) on the consumer purchasing behaviour within the geographical confines of Abia state, specifically in relation to the acquisition of online products. Henceforth, the scholar posits that the discoveries and propositions of this investigation would augment and reignite the proclivity of consumers in Abia state, Nigeria to engage in the acquisition of commodities and amenities via electronic means.

Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this research endeavor is to examine the impact of digital marketing on the

purchasing patterns exhibited by consumers of online merchandise within the geographical confines of Abia state, situated in the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The delineated objectives encompass to:

- Investigate potential existence of a statistically significant and positive correlation between Email marketing and customer purchasing behavior in the context of online product consumption in Abia state, Nigeria.
- Ascertain the presence of a statistically significant association between social media marketing and the purchasing behavior of customers with regards to online products within the geographical region of Abia state, Nigeria.
- Evaluate the correlation between online advertising and consumer purchasing behavior in Abia state, Nigeria, specifically focusing on consumers of online items.
- Ascertain the potential correlation between mobile marketing and customer purchasing behavior of online products in Abia state, Nigeria, further investigation is required.

Research Questions

The present investigation has formulated the ensuing research inquiries with the intention of providing a guiding framework for the study. They exist in a state of being;

- ❖ What is the magnitude of the statistically significant and positive correlation between Email marketing and customer purchasing behavior of online products in Abia state, Nigeria?
- ❖ What is the magnitude of the notable correlation between social media marketing and

customer purchasing behavior of online products in Abia state, Nigeria?

- ❖ To what extent does a relationship exist between online advertising and the purchase behavior of customers of online items in Abia state, Nigeria?
- ❖ What is the magnitude of the statistically significant association between mobile marketing and consumer purchasing behavior of online products within the context of Abia state, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses have been formulated in this study and they are in line with the specific objectives and research questions of this study.

H01: There is no statistically significant and positive correlation between email marketing strategies and online product purchases in Abia state, Nigeria.

H02: The correlation between social media marketing and consumer purchasing behavior in the context of online products within Abia state is not found to be statistically significant.

H03: There is no association between online advertising and customer purchasing behavior for online products in Abia state, Nigeria.

H04: There is no association between mobile marketing and online goods purchases in Abia State Nigeria.

Literature Review

This chapter of the research work has been organized into sections. This structure has been implemented to enhance the clarity and understanding of the presented information.

Conceptual Review

This subsection of this study was dedicated to the review of the concepts that are relevant to the study at hand. They are showcased below.

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing, colloquially referred to as internet marketing or web-based marketing, pertains to the utilization of the internet and its associated computerized technologies to accomplish marketing objectives and facilitate marketing endeavors encompassing the provision of superior services, management of supply chains, and cultivation of customer relationships (Liam, 2020). Similarly, digital marketing encompasses the utilization of electronic devices, specifically computers, to establish connections with consumers or customers. The aforementioned devices encompass tablets, mobile phones, and other similar technological apparatuses, which have effectively obviated traditional marketing methodologies, thereby facilitating the proliferation of marketing blends. As posited by Al-Azzam and Al-Mizeed (2021), the advent of digital marketing has emerged as a novel and transformative approach within the realm of marketing, thereby presenting unprecedented prospects for enterprises to engage in commercial activities. Once more, the aforementioned phenomenon can be characterized as a paradigm shift in the realm of marketing, wherein technological advancements serve as the catalyst for the emergence of novel concepts within the business landscape.

As per the scholarly work of Rai (2018), the remarkable progress of digital marketing has engendered enhancements in the strategies and methodologies employed by brands and enterprises in harnessing digital technology and platforms for their marketing pursuits. As per the scholarly work of Maha and Ranj (2016), a prevailing consensus has emerged indicating the escalating efficiency and efficacy of digital marketing campaigns. The aforementioned phenomenon can be ascribed to the seamless amalgamation of digital platforms within the realm of marketing strategies, coupled with the pervasive embrace of digital devices in the quotidian existence of individuals. Consequently, individuals are electing to utilise digital devices as opposed to engaging in the physical act of visiting brick-and-mortar establishments. Hence, the utilisation of digital marketing strategies enables marketing professionals to effectively enhance the accessibility of their products to a diverse audience by leveraging various digital platforms such as email marketing, mobile marketing, and other analogous channels.

E-Mail Marketing

Lodhi and Shoaib (2017), as referenced by Al-Azzam and Al-Mizeed (2021), have elucidated that e-mail marketing represents a form of direct marketing wherein electronic mail serves as the medium for conveying messages or engaging with the targeted recipients. It is an indisputable fact that electronic mail marketing continues to be one of the prominent digital marketing strategies employed for the dissemination of orders or targeted correspondence to

homogeneous individuals at a predetermined juncture. The utilisation of email as a communication medium provides businesses with the opportunity to effectively distribute tailored messages that align with and cater to the specific requirements of their intended clientele (Ugonna et al., 2017). E-mail, as a pivotal component of marketing strategies, facilitates the transmission of brand value propositions to the intended target market.

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is viewed as an emerging trend and a swiftly expanding method for effectively, efficiently, and easily communicating with specific target consumers. According to Omenugha (2018), the digital platform in question facilitates the establishment and growth of social networks among individuals and businesses through interactive dialogue and user participation. (Bansal et al., 2014) Social media platforms are used to advertise and facilitate the commercial transactions of a company's merchandise. In addition, typical social media manifestations include prominent platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, WhatsApp, Instagram, and YouTube. Social media platforms play an essential role in facilitating marketers' efforts to engage in deep and meaningful conversations with consumers and customers. Social media platforms include websites and applications that facilitate the instantaneous, uncomplicated, efficient, and effective dissemination of content by users. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010) Social media is a wrap of internet-based applications designed for the use

of web 2.0 technology that facilitate the creation and interchange of content.

Online Advertising

Online advertising possesses the power and competence to disseminate information to the intended audience while also persuading customers to engage in purchasing behavior. The strategic operation of online advertising marketing involves leveraging the internet to generate website traffic and distribute targeted marketing communications to desired potential consumers (Budiman, 2021).

According to Khan and Islam (2017), online advertising is recognized for its ability to promote products without being limited by geographical borders or limitations. Email marketing is a crucial and strategic component of digital marketing that plays a significant role in disseminating information about products or services offered by companies. Online advertising offers the potential to effectively engage with a wide range of consumers, promoting brand awareness and driving sales for a company across several online platforms (Dhore & Godbole, 2019).

Mobile Marketing

Mobile marketing has been widely acknowledged as a comprehensive, cost-effective, expeditious, and contemporary marketing avenue that empowers users to effortlessly acquire information and access appealing product attributes, all while facilitating the transactional process without necessitating the physical presence of the buyer at the goods' location (Alam et al., 2015). The aforementioned study conducted by Tiffany et al. (2018) elucidates the

notion that a conducive environment is established, thereby affording consumers the opportunity to exercise discernment and mindfulness in their procurement choices. Mobile marketing encompasses a plethora of captivating and interactive communication modalities that facilitate the exchange of information between enterprises and consumers. In pursuit of this objective, the scholarly work conducted by Mohamed et al. (2016) elucidated that mobile marketing encompasses a collection of methodologies that facilitate the seamless and meaningful exchange of information between organisations and their target demographics, leveraging the ubiquity of mobile devices and networks.

Consumer Buying Behavior

Consumer purchasing behavior can be delineated as the cognitive, affective, and behavioral processes that individuals undertake in the course of evaluating, acquiring, employing, and disposing of goods and services in order to fulfil their inherent needs and aspirations (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2009). Likewise, it encompasses the procurement and other consumption-related endeavours of individuals actively involved in the process of exchange.

The primary objective of customer relationship management is to gather comprehensive data regarding the wants and preferences of customers, with the aim of enhancing customer satisfaction and fostering increased purchasing behaviour. By establishing a strong customer relationship, firms can effectively discourage customers from migrating to alternative competitors, hence mitigating the associated costs involved (Castagna et al., 2020). According to Auf, Meddour, Saoula, and Majid (2018), the field of consumer behaviour pertains to the examination of individuals' demands, motives, and cognitive processes involved in the selection of one product over another, as well as the

purchasing patterns of various commodities and services. According to their assertions, consumer behaviour encompasses more than the mere act of physically purchasing items. Instead, it encompasses a broad spectrum of actions that span from the initial stage of problem awareness through post-purchase conduct, including the development of ideas and experiences aimed at fulfilling their needs and aspirations. Consumer purchasing behaviour provides insights on the preferences of consumers (Auf et al., 2018) and their level of satisfaction (Rajan et al., 2021). Rajan et al. (2021) claim that consumer satisfaction serves as an evaluative metric to gauge the extent to which a company's offerings, encompassing both products and services, align with or exceed customer anticipations. Nevertheless, the task of determining consumer happiness is a crucial factor in assessing a company's performance in relation to its financial gains and losses.

Accordingly, as articulated by Kumar (2016), the phenomenon of consumer purchasing behaviour encompasses the intricate progression through which individuals discern their inherent desires, amass pertinent information, assess various alternatives, and ultimately arrive at a definitive determination regarding the act of acquisition. The phenomenon in question may also be perceived as a sequence of deliberate decisions undertaken by a consumer prior to engaging in a purchase transaction, commencing subsequent to the customer's manifestation of a predisposition to procure a product or service. As per the scholarly work of Roy and Datta (2022), the intricate phenomenon of consumer buying behaviour can be comprehended as an amalgamation of multifaceted factors encompassing the discerning inclinations, perspectives, aspirations, and deliberations of the consumer, which subsequently manifest in

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their market-driven responses during the acquisition of a particular product or service.

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization, 2023 (Conceptual Framework)

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework of the study.

Theoretical Framework

There are so many theories that have direct connection to the study of digital marketing and they are considered below.

Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

This theory was proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen in 1975, and it has its origins in social psychology. The theory proposes three fundamental concepts: behavioural intention (BI), attitude (A), and subjective norms (SN). Equally, the theory held that a person's behavioural intentions are heavily influenced by his attitude and subjective norms. Again, the theory can be interpreted mathematically to imply that behavioural intention is the sum of attitude and

subjective norms. Likewise, if a person's intention to conduct in a particular manner is strong enough, it is likely to be translated into action.

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The theory under consideration was postulated by Icek Ajzen in the year 1991 and represents an expansion of the theory of reasoned action (TRA) originally proposed by Martin Fishbein and Ajzen in 1975. The theoretical framework known as (TPB) integrates the concept of perceived behavioural control (PBC) into the constructs of attitudes and subjective norms, which serve as fundamental elements within the (TRA). Perceived behavioural control pertains to the subjective evaluation made by individuals regarding the degree of facilitation or hindrance

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entailed in the enactment of a particular behaviour. Nonetheless, it deviates from Rotter's (1966) conceptualization of perceived locus of control, as it exhibits a dynamic nature, subject to fluctuations in accordance with the diverse array of events experienced by the individual. The concept of perceived locus of control is widely recognised as a highly versatile cognitive expectation that demonstrates a notable degree of constancy across diverse contexts.

The Social Cognitive Theory (SCT)

Bandura proposed this theory in 1986, focusing on the concept of self-efficacy, which is defined as the perception of one's capacity to use technology to complete a specific job or task. According to the theory, the user's behaviour is influenced by their expectations of personal and performance-related benefits. Consequently, self-efficacy influences both categories of outcome expectations. Again, while a person's esteem and sense of accomplishment relate to personal outcome expectations, outcome expectations relate to job performance, which leads to performance-related expectations (Sharma & Mishra, 2014).

Technology Adoption Model (TAM)

The aforementioned model was postulated by Davis in the year 1989 and has since gained significant traction in the realm of technology adoption research. The inherent efficacy of the model resides within its fundamental simplicity, characterized by the presence of solely two constructs, namely perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. These constructs serve as the bedrock for prognosticating the degree of adoption of novel technologies at the individual

level. Henceforth, the concept of perceived usefulness pertains to the extent to which an individual harbours the belief that the utilisation of a specific system would augment their occupational proficiency. Conversely, perceived ease of use denotes the extent to which an individual holds the conviction that employing a particular system would entail minimal exertion. Based on the aforementioned considerations, the present investigation is predicated upon the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), an established theoretical framework that has emerged from the theory of reasoned action (TRA) and incorporates the inclusion of perceived behavioural control within its conceptual constructs. This assertion is substantiated by the recognition that, notwithstanding an individual's attitude and subjective norms, there must also exist a profound conviction regarding the perceived level of ease or difficulty associated with engaging in the behaviour under consideration, as expounded by the theory of planned behaviour.

Empirical Review

The following scholarly published research works were reviewed empirically in order to guide this study in this section of this study. They are;

AL-Azzam and AL-Mizeed (2021) examined how digital marketing affects customer purchases. This scholarly inquiry will examine Jordan's history, culture, socio-economic dynamics, and political landscape. This study uses a case study approach to illuminate multifactor This study examined how internet marketing affects

Jordanian university students' consumer behaviour. The study examined Jordan's digital marketing channels that can impact customer purchases. It also investigated which products clients buy on digital media. The study indicated that digital marketing and mobile marketing, strongly influences customer purchasing decisions. The hypothesis testing showed that Jordan has many popular digital media outlets that influence student behaviour. The research suggested that organisations should capitalise on digital and technological advances to increase brand recognition via digital platforms to stay competitive in the modern business landscape.

The study conducted by Hassan (2019) delved into the intricate relationship between digital marketing adoption and sales improvement within the context of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The primary objective of this research endeavour was to scrutinise the impact of digital marketing on the enhancement of sales performance in the aforementioned business sector. The study's primary data were obtained via a meticulously designed structured questionnaire administered to a randomly selected sample of respondents within the small and medium enterprises (SMEs) sector. The collected data underwent the application of both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses. The empirical evidence suggests that the implementation of digital marketing instruments, including but not limited to electronic mail, search engine optimisation, pay-per-click advertising, and online promotional activities, would yield substantial enhancements in the sales

performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The study posited that in order for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to maintain and enhance their sales performance within the sector, it is advisable for them to capitalise on a multitude of digital tools as integral components of their marketing strategies.

Garcia, Lizcano, Ramos, and Matos (2019) studied "Digital marketing actions that yield enhanced user attraction and loyalty: An analytical inquiry." This study sought to identify digital marketing's main user acquisition and retention methods. The Delphi method and in-depth interviews were used in this investigation. The study's findings reveal the key steps needed to acquire and retain users through digital marketing, according to domain experts. The results have identified the exact strategies needed to attract and keep users in business-to-consumer firms that utilise the internet's digital marketing ecosystem. The study's findings explain the key factors while ignoring session time and bounce rate, which do not affect business-to-consumer conversion optimisation. Bizhanova et al., (2019) examined how digital marketing has affected entrepreneurship. The present study examined the substantial effects of digital marketing on modern entrepreneurship and the main organisational framework-building tasks. Secondary data came from statistical and economic analysis. The empirical data show that digitalization is causing marketing executives problems. Organisations must navigate complex, rapidly changing marketplaces outside their control. The research shows that digital

marketing relies on internet-based channels that are frequently used. These channels are dynamic, changing frequently in reaction to market developments. Digital marketing involves periodic inspection, rigorous analysis, extensive interpretation, strategic dissemination, and builds strong consumer-brand partnerships.

Shah investigated "The Influence of Digital Marketing on Business and Politics." in 2018. The purpose of this study was to explain how digital marketing has increased involvement between firms, politicians, and Indians. The study found that 86% of marketers use websites and email marketing to reach the growing audience of smartphone-owning techies. It is well known that social media has greatly improved direct communication between political representatives and Indian citizens. Politicians are using social media to create virtual spaces where their constituents can discuss a variety of important topics. In conclusion, digital marketing methods have significantly increased contact between commercial firms, political entities, and the Indian subcontinent's population.

Garg, Bansal, and Singla conducted a study titled "Impact of Digital Marketing on Consumer Decision Making" in 2021. This study illustrates the effect of digital marketing on consumer choice. This study is descriptive in nature, and the observation method was used as the primary source of data. Secondary data were gathered from a variety of research publications, online and printed journals, periodicals, books, newspapers, government reports, and websites. The findings indicated that digital marketing

plays a crucial role in encouraging consumers to purchase products, leading to an increase in their overall preference list. Additionally, the study revealed a direct correlation between digital marketing and consumer decision making. Again, there is a direct effect on product demand, which will naturally increase a business or organization's sales. The research suggests that organisations should evaluate the accessibility of their digital facilities before launching any online products.

The study conducted by Rajkumar, Arya, and Verma (2019) delved into the examination of the influence exerted by digital marketing on customer purchasing behaviour. The focal point of this study resides in the significance of digital marketing for both marketers and consumers alike. Furthermore, it elucidates the impact of digital marketing on the consumer purchasing behaviour. In the present investigation, both primary and secondary data were employed. Once more, the present study is characterised by its analytical and descriptive research design. The empirical observations derived from this study have revealed that digital marketing serves as a catalyst in disseminating awareness pertaining to the realm of online shopping among prospective customers. Once more, it is imperative to acknowledge that digital marketing serves as the conduit through which pertinent information regarding products is disseminated in the online realm. The study further elucidated that social media marketing exhibits a discernible positive influence on the purchasing behavior of consumers.

Methodology

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The survey design method was adopted because it is a technique for eliciting responses from a group of individuals believed to possess the necessary information when queries are posed to them in the study area. The researcher employed a cross-sectional survey in which a cross-section of consumers of online products in the state of Abia were analyzed to determine how digital marketing impacted their purchasing behavior during the period under consideration. The primary data were collected using a questionnaire, while the secondary data were obtained from sources such as journals, textbooks, published and unpublished articles, and the internet. The study encompasses a population comprising civil servants, students, lecturers, and business persons who actively engage as consumers of online products and services within the Umuahia and Aba metropolis. The sample size for this study is excessively vast and indeterminate. Based on the aforementioned considerations, the researcher utilized Topman's method to determine the sample size. To do this, a pilot survey was conducted, consisting of a question pertaining to the study, which was presented to 20 participants who were asked to provide either a positive or negative response. The inquiry poses the following question: "What is the extent of the positive or negative influence exerted by digital marketing on the purchasing behaviour of consumers who engage in online transactions for products and services within Abia state?" The positive responses were 80% (0.80) of the total, whilst the negative responses accounted for 20% (0.20). Hence, the formula devised by Topman is provided as follows:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 Pq}{E^2}$$

Where: n = sample size; Z = standard deviation for desired level of confidence (1.96); P = probability of positive response; q = probability of negative response; and e = 5%, (0.05) the limit of tolerable error.

$$n = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.80 \times 0.20}{0.05^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.80 \times 0.20}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.614656}{0.0025} = 245$$

$$n = 245$$

Therefore the sample size for this study is 245 respondents. The researcher employed a convenience non-probability sampling technique.

Reliability test was executed with the Cronbach Alpha coefficient was used to analyse the scales' and their sources' internal consistency. The research instrument's construct validity was assessed using factor analysis. For this study, a factor loading level threshold of 0.5 is necessary. The information in Table 3.1 shows that any construct above 0.5 is considered reliable. The questionnaire was rigorously validated by qualified researchers. The demographic responses of the respondents were analysed using tables and simple percentages. The stated study hypotheses were assessed using multiple regressions at a significance level of 5%, utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0.

Table 3.1: Cronbach Alpha Test and Factor loading of Reliability and Validity of the instrument

S/No	Variables	No. of items	Cronbach Alpha	Factor Loading	Comments
1	Email Marketing	4	0.7624	0.7341	Accepted
2	Social Media	4	0.8962	0.6820	
3	Marketing	4	0.7842	0.6976	Accepted
4	Online Advertising	4	0.8665	0.7642	
5	Mobile Marketing	5	0.8572	0.7263	Accepted
	Consumer Buying Behaviour				Accepted Accepted

Source: SPSS output, 2023

The result of the SPSS output shows that all the variables met the minimum threshold for acceptance since they are up to 70% (0.70) and 50% (0.50) required for reliability and validity.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval

The distribution, retrieval and use of the copies of questionnaire are shown in the table below;

Table 4.1: Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval

Respondents	No. of copies of the questionnaire distributed	No. of copies of questionnaire returned/used	No. of copies of questionnaire not returned	Percentage of copies of questionnaire returned/used
Civil servants	75	60	15	29.0
Students	55	48	7	23.0
Lecturers	65	55	10	26.0
Business persons	50	45	5	22.0
Total	245	208 (85%)	37 (15%)	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

According to Table 4.1, 245 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to respondents, and 208 copies, or 85 percent, were returned and deemed usable for the study. Again, 75 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to public servants, of which 60 copies, or 29%, were returned and utilised for the study. 55 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to students,

of which 48 copies, or 23%, were returned and deemed usable for the study. 65 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to professors, of which 55 copies, or 26%, were retrieved and used for the study. While 50 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to businesspeople, only 45 copies, or 22%, were returned and utilised for this study.

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Demographics of Respondents

The table below consists of the demographic variables of this study.

Table 4.2: Demographics of the Respondents

Options	Frequency	Percentage
Gender:		
Male	124	59.6
Female	84	40.4
Total	208	100.0
Marital Status:		
Single	76	36.5
Married	114	54.8
Others	18	8.7
Total	208	100.0
Age Bracket:		
18 – 25yrs	26	12.5
26 – 30yrs	60	28.8
31 – 35yrs	59	28.4
36 – 40yrs	29	13.9
41yrs and above	34	16.3
Total	208	100.0
Educational Qualifications:		
WASC	36	17.3
OND	55	26.4
B.Sc./HND	76	37.5
Masters and Above	39	18.8
Total	208	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

According to Table 4.2, 124 (59.6%) of the respondents are male, while 84 (40.4%) are female. 76 (36.5%), 114 (54.8%), and 18 (8.7%) of the respondents, respectively, are unmarried, married, and divorced, widowed, or separated. 26 (12.5%), 60 (28.8%), 59 (28.4%), 29 (13.9%), and 34 (16.3%) of the respondents are 18 to 25 years old, 26 to 30 years old, 31 to 35 years old,

36 to 40 years old, and 41 years and older, respectively. 36 (17.3%), 55 (26.4%), 78 (37.5%), and 39 (18.8%) of the respondents possess a West African Secondary Certificate (WASC), an Ordinary National Diploma (OND), a Bachelor of Science/Higher National Diploma (B.Sc./HND), or a Master's Degree and Above, respectively.

ANALYSES ON MAJOR RESEARCH VARIABLES

**Table 4.3: Responses on Email Marketing
Email Marketing**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	16	7.7	7.7	7.7
Disagree	20	9.6	9.6	17.3
Undecided	13	6.3	6.3	23.6
Agree	72	34.6	34.6	58.2
Strongly Agree	87	41.8	41.8	100.0
Total	208	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The tabulated data illustrates that within the study area, a proportion of 7.7% (n=16) of the respondents exhibited a strong disagreement, while 9.6% (n=20) expressed a disagreement, and 6.3% (n=13) remained undecided regarding the impact of digital marketing on consumer purchasing behaviour of online products.

Conversely, a significant portion of 34.6% (n=72) of the respondents displayed agreement, while the majority, comprising 41.8% (n=87), strongly agreed with the notion that digital marketing indeed contributes to the consumer buying behaviour of online products in the aforementioned study area.

**Table 4.4 Responses on Social Media Marketing
Social Media Marketing**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	15	7.2	7.2	7.2
Disagree	15	7.2	7.2	14.4
Undecided	17	8.2	8.2	22.6
Agree	81	38.9	38.9	61.5
Strongly Agree	80	38.5	38.5	100.0
Total	208	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

According to the data shown in the table, it can be observed that a proportion of 7.2% of respondents strongly disagreed, another 7.2%

disagreed, 8.2% were undecided, 38.9% agreed, and 38.5% strongly agreed with the notion that digital marketing has a positive impact on

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customer buying behaviour of online products within the study area.

Table 4.5 Responses on Online Advertising
Online Advertising

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	18	8.7	8.7	8.7
Disagree	22	10.6	10.6	19.2
Undecided	5	2.4	2.4	21.6
Agree	33	15.9	15.9	37.5
Strongly Agree	130	62.5	62.5	100.0
Total	208	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

According to the table, it was revealed that a proportion of 8.7% (n=18), 10.6% (n=22), 2.4% (n=5), 15.9% (n=33), and 62.5% (n=130) of the participants expressed strong disagreement, disagreement, indecision, agreement, and strong agreement, respectively, about the impact of digital marketing on customer purchasing behaviour of online items in Abia state, Nigeria.

Table 4.6 Responses on Mobile Marketing

Mobile Marketing

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	28	13.5	13.5	13.5
Disagree	26	12.5	12.5	26.0
Undecided	14	6.7	6.7	32.7
Agree	54	26.0	26.0	58.7
Strongly Agree	86	41.3	41.3	100.0
Total	208	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

According to the data shown in the table, it can be observed that a proportion of 13.5% (n=28) of the respondents strongly disagreed, 12.5% (n=26) disagreed, 6.7% (n=14) were undecided, 26% (n=54) agreed, and 41.3% (n=86) strongly agreed with the notion that digital marketing has a positive impact on consumer buying behaviour of online products within the research region.

**Table 4.7 Responses on Consumer Buying Behaviour
Consumer Buying Behaviour**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	25	12.0	12.0	12.0
Disagree	11	5.3	5.3	17.3
Undecided	9	4.3	4.3	21.6
Agree	64	30.8	30.8	52.4
Strongly Agree	99	47.6	47.6	100.0
Total	208	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

According to the data in the table, 25 (12%), 11 (5.3%), 9 (4.3%), 64 (30.8%), and 99 (47.6%) of the respondents strongly disagreed, disagreed, were unsure, agreed, and highly agreed that digital marketing influences consumers' online product purchasing decisions in the study region.

Test of Hypotheses

The evaluation of digital marketing was conducted by measuring four independent variables against a dependent variable, consumer buying behaviour, using regression analysis as the methodological framework.

Test of Hypothesis one

HO1: There is no statistically significant and positive relationship between Email marketing and buying behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state, Nigeria.

H1: There is statistically significant and positive relationship between Email marketing and buying behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state, Nigeria.

The data in tables 4.3 and 4.7 were used to test this hypothesis. The SPSS output is shown below;

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Consumer Buying Behaviour	3.9663	1.34912	208
Email Marketing	3.9327	1.24927	208

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.822 ^a	.790	.683	1.31587	2.410

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- a. Predictors: (Constant), Email Marketing
b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.073	1	20.073	11.593	.001 ^b
	Residual	356.691	206	1.732		
	Total	376.764	207			

- a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour
b. Predictors: (Constant), Email Marketing

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.986	.302		9.887	.000
	Email Marketing	.249	.073	.231	34.049	.001

- a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

Interpretation of the SPSS output

The R-value presented in the model summary table indicates a robust and statistically significant positive correlation of 0.822. The coefficient of determination, denoted as R², serves as a measure of the proportion of the total variability exhibited by the dependent variable, namely consumer buying behaviour, that can be elucidated by the independent variable of interest, specifically email marketing. This empirical evidence demonstrates that the utilisation of email marketing strategies exhibits a statistically significant association with approximately 79 percent of the observed variance in consumer purchasing behaviour.

This observation exhibits a significantly elevated magnitude. The comprehensive regression model demonstrates a statistically significant prediction of the outcome of the variables, as indicated by a p-value of 0.001, which is below the predetermined significance level of 0.05. Furthermore, the t-value of 34.049 further supports the robustness of the model's predictive capabilities. Indeed, it can be inferred that the aforementioned proposition aligns favourably with the given context. Once more, the presence of non-serial autocorrelation is negated by the Durbin Watson statistic of (2.410), surpassing the lower threshold as documented in relevant tables and falling within the permissible range.

Decision:

The null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis based on the statistical analysis. This decision is supported by the P-value (0.001) being lower than the predetermined significance level (Alpha = 0.05), and the calculated t-value (34.049) exceeding the critical t-value (1.960). These results indicate a statistically significant and positive association between Email marketing and consumer

purchasing behaviour for online products in Abia state, Nigeria. **Test of Hypothesis Two**

H02: Social media marketing does not significantly relate to buying behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state.

H2: Social media marketing significantly relate to buying behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state.

The data for testing of this hypothesis were drawn from tables 4.4 and 4.7. The SPSS result is shown below;

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Consumer Buying Behaviour	3.9663	1.34912	208
Social Media Marketing	3.9423	1.18629	208

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.871 ^a	.783	.640	1.33963	1.402

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Marketing

b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.077	1	7.077	13.943	.000 ^b
	Residual	369.688	206	1.795		
	Total	376.764	207			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Marketing

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.581	.323		14.179	.000
	Social Media Marketing	.156	.078	.137	31.986	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

Interpretation of the SPSS output

The model summary table shows an R-value of 0.871, indicating a robust, statistically significant, and positively orientated association. R² measures how much of the overall variability in the dependent variable, consumer buying behaviour, can be explained by the independent variable, social media marketing. This empirical research shows that social media marketing accounts for 78% of consumer purchase behaviour variance. This observation has a large magnitude. The full regression model predicts outcome variables with a P-value of 0.000, below the significance level of 0.05. The 31.986 t-value supports the idea that the model fits the data well. The Durbin Watson statistic of (1.402) again disproves serial auto correlation by exceeding the lower criterion in previous tables and remaining within the allowed range.

Decision:

Since the P-value (0.000) is below the significance level (Alpha = 0.05), the alternate hypothesis replaced the null hypothesis. The estimated t-value (31.986) exceeds the threshold t-value (1.960), showing a statistically significant correlation between social media marketing and online product purchases in Abia state, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: There is no relationship that exists between online advertising and buying behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state, Nigeria.

H₃: There is a relationship that exists between online advertising and buying behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state, Nigeria.

The data in tables 4.5 and 4.7 were utilized to test this hypothesis. The SPSS result is shown below;

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Consumer Buying Behaviour	3.9663	1.34912	208
Online Advertising	4.1298	1.35756	208

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Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.802 ^a	.700	.620	1.33540	2.384

a. Predictors: (Constant), Online Advertising

b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.408	1	9.408	15.276	.002 ^b
	Residual	367.357	206	1.783		
	Total	376.764	207			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Online Advertising

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.318	.297		11.165	.000
	Online Advertising	.157	.068	.158	22.969	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

Interpretation of the SPSS output

The model summary table shows an R-value of 0.802, indicating a strong and positive link. R² measures how much of the total variability in the dependent variable (customer buying behaviour) can be explained by the independent variable (online advertising). This shows that online advertising may account for up to 70% of consumer purchase behaviour variation. Its worth is also greatly increased. The whole regression model predicts variables statistically with a p-value of 0.002, below the significance

level of 0.05. Additionally, the model's 22.969 t-value indicates its strong fit. The Durbin Watson value of (2.384) exceeds the bottom bound in tables and falls inside the allowed range, indicating no serial autocorrelation.

Decision:

The null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis due to the observation that the P-value (0.002) is smaller than the predetermined significance level (Alpha = 0.05). Additionally, the calculated t-value (22.969)

exceeds the critical t-value (1.960), indicating the presence of a statistically significant relationship between online advertising and consumer purchasing behaviour in the context of online products within Abia state, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Four

HO4: Mobile marketing does not have any significant relationship with buying behaviour of

consumers of online products in Abia state, Nigeria.

H4: Mobile marketing has a significant relationship with buying behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state, Nigeria.

The data for the testing of this hypothesis were derived from tables 4.6 and 4.7 respectively. The SPSS result is shown below;

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Consumer Buying Behaviour	3.9663	1.34912	208
Mobile Marketing	3.6923	1.45181	208

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.850 ^a	.820	.714	1.33935	1.400

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Marketing

b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.227	1	7.227	14.029	.005 ^b
	Residual	369.537	206	1.794		
	Total	376.764	207			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

b. Predictors: (Constant), Mobile Marketing

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.442	.254		17.465	.000
	Mobile Marketing	.129	.064	.138	20.072	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Buying Behaviour

Interpretation of the SPSS output

The R-value of the model summary table is 0.850, indicating a highly significant and positive correlation. The R2 value indicates the proportion of the total variation in the dependent variable (consumer purchasing behaviour) that can be explained by the independent variable (Mobile marketing). This demonstrates that mobile marketing could account for 82% of the variance in consumer purchasing behaviour. Also extremely expensive. The total regression model has a sig (P-value) of (0.005), which is less than Alpha (0.05), and a t-value of 20.072 (That is, it is a decent fit). Again, the absence of serial autocorrelation is indicated by the Durbin

Watson value of 1,400, which is greater than the table's lower limit and falls within the acceptable range.

Decision:

The null hypothesis is rejected in favour of the alternate hypothesis due to the observation that the P-value (0.005) is less than the predetermined significance level (Alpha = 0.05). Furthermore, the calculated t-value (20.072) surpasses the critical t-value (1.960), thus indicating a statistically significant association between mobile marketing and the purchasing behaviour of online product consumers in Abia state, Nigeria.

Figure 4.1 Heuristic model of the study.
Source: Researcher’s conceptualization, 2023.

Discussion of Findings

This study's primary objective was to investigate the impact of digital marketing indices on the purchasing behaviour of consumers of online products in Abia state, Nigeria. The study found,

however, that all four dimensions of digital marketing (Email marketing, Social media marketing, Online advertising, and Mobile marketing) have a positive and statistically significant relationship with the purchasing

behaviour of online product consumers in Abia state, Nigeria. The findings are consistent with previous studies by Hassan (2019), AL-Azzam and AL-Mizeed (2021), and Amoah and Jibril (2021), which confirmed that each of the digital marketing dimensions used here is significantly related to the purchasing behaviour of online product consumers in the study area. Again, this finding validates the findings of Rajkumar et al. (2019), namely that digital marketing raises customers' awareness of online purchasing and provides online product information. However, the findings of Liam (2020); Garcia et al. (2019) and Garg et al. (2020) validate the findings of the study, that there is a significant relationship between digital marketing techniques such as social media, search engine optimisation ads, and emails and the development of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). It also identified the specific steps that must be taken to attract and retain users in business-to-consumer companies that utilise the digital marketing ecosystem on the internet. In a similar vein, Bizhanova et al., (2019) invalidates the findings, as their findings revealed that growing digitalization is causing serious problems for marketing executives as they confront uncontrollable markets that are growing, complex, and rapidly changing. Shah (2018) introduced the political aspect of digital marketing, as he discovered that social media have facilitated greater direct communication between legislators and Indian citizens.

Summary of Findings

The following findings were made during the course of carrying out this study. They are;

- ❖ This study found a statistically significant and positive relationship between Email marketing and the purchasing behaviour of online product consumers in Abia state, Nigeria, as illustrated by the responses of the respondents.
- ❖ The study also found that social media marketing has a significant correlation with the purchasing behaviour of Abia state online consumers.
- ❖ The study posited that a significant correlation exists between online advertising and the purchasing behaviour of consumers of online products within the geographical confines of Abia state, Nigeria.
- ❖ The study also revealed that mobile marketing has a significant correlation with the purchasing behaviour of online product consumers in Abia state, Nigeria.

Conclusion

The adoption of digital marketing has garnered widespread acceptance among firms, governments, and individuals across both developed and developing economies, owing to its profound capacity to augment management processes and bolster financial performances. The subject matter pertains to the utilisation of technology within marketing endeavours, thereby possessing the potential to facilitate the process of locating and potentially acquiring product concepts or information for prospective and current consumers through the act of perusing the digital realm or various websites. Nevertheless, the present investigation has substantiated these suppositions, as the results demonstrate a noteworthy and affirmative

correlation between the various digital marketing indices/proxies, namely email marketing and mobile marketing, and the purchasing behaviour of online product consumers in Abia state, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following far reaching recommendations deduced from the findings of the study were made here;

- There should be concerted efforts aimed at increasing and sustaining the creation of awareness about the efficacy of email marketing in relation to the purchasing behaviour of online product consumers in Abia state, Nigeria. This will significantly increase the profitability of those companies in the studied area that conduct online business.
- It is imperative to enhance the user-friendliness of social media platforms, regardless of the users' educational backgrounds, in order to foster a profound sense of inclusivity. This, in turn, will lead to the gratification of the consumer and subsequently engender their unwavering loyalty.
- Online advertising should be given undivided attention and its proper position in the grand scheme of things because the majority of respondents to this study are familiar with online platforms that can disseminate the advertising of firms and their products. If this is executed properly, the required level of patronage can be attained optimally.
- There should be a seasonal evaluation of how mobile marketing has performed in the study area, as well as potential improvement initiatives, to avoid cognitive dissonance among

consumers, who are the king and the reason why businesses exist.

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